

A NEW SYNTHETIC ROUTE TO POLYCYCLIC HYDRO- AROMATIC COMPOUNDS. SYNTHESIS OF 2:3-BENZ- BICYCLO-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -OCTENE.

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A general scheme for the synthesis of mono, bi, tri, and polynuclear hydroaromatic compounds has been described in the present communication. A synthesis of 2:3-benz-bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -octene has been achieved by an application of the above method. Attempt has also been made to synthesise hexahydropentanthrylenemethane.

The object of this investigation is the exploitation of a new method of synthesis of polycyclic hydroaromatic compounds having oestrogenic and carcinogenic activity.

The method consists in condensing the sodium salt of the dicyano ester formed by the condensation of an aldehyde-cyanohydrin with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate with a monohalogenated ester to yield the product (A). This on hydrolysis gives an acid, the triethyl ester of which; when subjected to Dieckmanns, condensation, yields the product (B). The ester (B) on hydrolysis and decarboxylation yields a keto-acid, which serves as the starting material in building up other types of ring systems.

where R is either alkyl or other ring system and n may have values ranging from 1 to 3.

For the synthesis of 2:3-benz-bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -octene (VII) the following method has been adopted. Benzaldehyde-cyanohydrin is allowed to react with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate when the sodium derivative of ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -phenylpropionate (A, R=Ph) is obtained. It is allowed to react with ethyl β -chloropropionate when diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- α -phenyl- n -butane- $\beta\delta$ -dicarboxylate (I) is obtained. When hydrolysed by means of sulphuric acid the latter yields an acid, the triethyl ester (II) of which undergoes cyclisation in presence of sodium in benzene to yield diethyl 2-phenylcyclopentanone-3:5-dicarboxylate (III).

This ester on hydrolysis and decarboxylation, yields 2-phenylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (IV). 2:3-Benz-bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -octene-4-one (VI), obtained by the Clemmensen reduction and subsequent ring-closure of the keto-acid (IV) yields the required hydrocarbon (VII) on reduction.

For the synthesis of hexahydropentanthrylenemethane the ethyl ester of the keto-acid (IV) is condensed with ethyl bromoacetate by Reformatsky's reaction to give diethyl 2-phenylcyclopentanol-3-carboxylate-1-acetate (VIII). This is dehydrated to the corresponding unsaturated ester (IX) by Darzen's method and hydrogenated to diethyl 2-phenylcyclopentane-3-carboxylate-1-acetate (X). This ester on hydrolysis yields the corresponding dibasic acid which by internal Friedel-Craft's reaction, is converted into a substance which seems to be 8-ketohexahydropentanthryleneketone (XI).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

or

Incidentally it might be mentioned that the above method is equally suitable for the synthesis of tricarboxylic acids with the carboxyl groups attached to three different carbon atoms, as well as for the synthesis of cyclohexane and cyclopentane derivatives.

Similar compounds have been obtained from benzaldehyde-cyanohydrin and ethyl γ -bromobutyrate and this will be the subject of the next communication. Investigations are in progress with other ring systems.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

*Diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- α -phenyl-*n*-butane- $\beta\delta$ -dicarboxylate (I).*—Sodium (11.6 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (140 c. c.) and ethyl cyanoacetate (56 g.) added. Mandelic nitrile (66 g.) was then added to the alcoholic solution containing the insoluble sodium compound in suspension, in small quantities at a time. Considerable heat was generated after each addition, and the temperature was regulated by cooling. When all the nitrile had been added, the sodium compound passed into solution and the clear, brown liquid was allowed to stand for 12 hours for the completion of the reaction. The mixture was mixed with ethyl β -chloropropionate (64 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated was boiled under reflux for about 15 hours. The filtered liquid was diluted with water and extracted with ether; the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and the ether removed. The dicyano ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b. p. 218–22°/5 mm., yield 85 g. (Found: C, 65.7; H, 6.4. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 65.8; H, 6.09 per cent).

The major portion of the liquid became solid on standing in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid, oily impurities removed on porous plate and then recrystallised from ethyl alcohol. The ethyl ester was then obtained in colourless crystals, m. p. 81°. (Found: N, 9.0. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.5 per cent).

*α -Phenyl-*n*-butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid.*—The foregoing ester (20 c. c.) was mixed with sulphuric acid (70%, 120 c. c.) and boiled under reflux for 12 hours, the condenser being removed from time to time to allow

the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water, extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution was treated with sodium carbonate. On acidification of the carbonate solution the acid was obtained partly in the form of its acid-anhydride, which was heated on a water-bath with a solution of caustic alkali (15%) for 3-4 hours. The alkali solution was then acidified and extracted with ether. After removing ether the product was kept in a desiccator where it solidified. It crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m. p. 185° (decomp.), yield 10 g. (Found : C, 58.64 ; H, 5.29. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 58.6 ; H, 5.2 per cent).

Triethyl α -Phenyl-n-butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (II).—It was obtained in an almost quantitative yield from the acid by the alcohol vapour method. In a typical experiment the acid (30 g.), absolute alcohol (100 c. c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (9 c. c.), 3 litres of vapourised alcohol (3-4 hours) gave 35 g. of the ester, b. p. 187-94°/5 mm. (Found : C, 65.4 ; H, 7.3. $C_{19}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 65.1 ; H, 7.4 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Phenylcyclopentanone-3 : 5-dicarboxylate (III).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (30 g.) and molecular sodium (4 g.) in dry benzene (75 c. c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and it was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a reddish violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil (18 g.), b. p. 184-92°/5 mm. (Found : C, 67.6 ; H, 6.5. $C_{17}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 67.1 ; H, 6.5 per cent).

2-Phenylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic Acid (IV).—The ester (III., 10 g.) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether, and the extract washed with water and dried. After removing the ether it was kept in a desiccator where it crystallised. Recrystallised from ether it melted at 114-15°. (Found : C, 70.8 ; H, 6.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6 ; H, 5.8 per cent).

2-Phenylcyclopentanone-1-carboxylic Acid (V).—The pure keto-acid (IV, 5 g.), amalgamated zinc (40 g.), and concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c. c.) were refluxed for 12 hours, more acid (40 c. c.) was then added and the heating continued for 12 hours. By extraction with ether a product was obtained which showed no properties of a ketone and boiled at 185-90°/10 mm. (Found : C, 75.6 ; H, 7.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 75.7 ; H, 7.3 per cent).

2:3-Benz-bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -octene-4-one (VI).—The foregoing acid (4 g.) was converted into its chloride by 1 hour's boiling with thionyl chloride (25 c.c.), excess of thionyl chloride being subsequently removed on the water-bath under reduced pressure. An ice-cold carbon disulphide solution (25 c.c.) of the chloride was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) kept at 0° for 3 hours, the whole was heated to boiling and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. After working up in the usual manner the product was distilled at 127-32°/10 mm. (Found: C, 83.6; H, 6.8. $C_{12}H_{12}O$ requires C, 83.72; H, 6.9 per cent). The semicarbazone had m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 18.1. $C_{12}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 18.3 per cent).

2:3-Benz-bicyclo-[0:3:3]- Δ^2 -octene (VII).—The foregoing ketone (2 g.) was reduced by boiling for 10 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.), water (40 c.c.) and amalgamated zinc (40 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) being added after each hour. The hydrocarbon was separated with ether and distilled, b.p. 118°-24°/9 mm. (Found: C, 91.7; H, 8.8. $C_{12}H_{14}$ requires C, 91.1; H, 8.8 per cent).

Ethyl 2-Phenylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylate, prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (10 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, or by esterifying overnight with alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride, formed a crystalline solid (10 g.). Recrystallised from alcohol, it melts at 60°. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 6.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.8 per cent). The semicarbazone crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 173°. (Found: N, 14.68. $C_{16}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires N, 14.53 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Phenylcyclopentanol-3-carboxylate-1-acetate (VIII).—A mixture of ethyl 3-phenylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylate (5 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (3.6 g.), dry zinc filings (purified by washing first with warm alkali and then with absolute alcohol and dry ether, 3 g.), dry and pure benzene (25 c.c.) was warmed on the water-bath until a reaction set in. The vigorous reaction caused the mixture to boil for 10 minutes without external heating. When this had subsided, the whole was boiled for 6 hours, and the product decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, washed, dried, and distilled. The hydroxy ester (5 g.) had b.p. 190-97°/6 mm. (Found: C, 67.26; H, 7.05. $C_{18}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 67.5; H, 7.5 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Phenyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentenylacetate-3-carboxylate (IX).—Thionyl chloride (2.8 c.c.) was added slowly to a well-stirred ice-cold mixture of the foregoing hydroxy-ester (10 g.), anhydrous ether (30 c.c.) and pure pyridine (5 c.c.). Stirring and cooling were continued for 2 hours, the solution was then poured into ice-water, and ethereal solution was washed, dried, and distilled. Diethyl 2-phenyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentenylacetate-3-carboxylate formed a light

yellow liquid, b.p. $184^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, 71.61; H, 7.13. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.52; H, 7.2 per cent).

Diethyl 2-Phenylcyclopentane-3-carboxylate-1-acetate (X).—The distilled unsaturated ester was hydrogenated in absolute alcoholic solution, platinum oxide catalyst being used. 6 G. of the substance in alcohol (50 c.c.) were shaken for 12 hours with platinum oxide (0.5 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen when the theoretical quantity of hydrogen was absorbed. Diethyl 2-phenylcyclopentane-3-carboxylate-1-acetate boiled at $175-77^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, 70.4; H, 7.68. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 71.0; H, 7.8 per cent).

2-Phenylcyclopentane-3-carboxylic-1-acetic Acid.—It was obtained by refluxing diethyl 2-phenylcyclopentane-3-carboxylate-1-acetate with alcoholic potash for 2 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and after dilution the unchanged ester was removed by means of ether. The aqueous layer was concentrated and after acidification the free acid was extracted with ether, the ether removed and the product kept in a vacuum desiccator when it solidified. It was finally crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. $170-73^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 67.85; H, 6.39. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.7; H, 6.4 per cent).

8-Ketohexahydropentanthryleneketone (XI).—The dibasic acid from the ester (X, 4 g.) was converted into its chloride by boiling with thionyl chloride (40 c.c.) for 2 hours, the excess of thionyl chloride being then removed on the water-bath under reduced pressure. A solution of the chloride in carbon disulphide at 0° was treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.). After being kept in ice for 2 hours the whole was heated to boiling and then decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. After removing carbon disulphide it was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and distilled. A small fraction (0.1 g.), probably (XI), obtained on distillation (the boiling point could not be recorded, as very small quantity of the substance was obtained) was analysed. (Found : C, 78.1; H, 5.9. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 79.2; H, 5.6 per cent).

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